

Traceability and Quality Monitoring throughout the Fish Value Chain

D4.2 Risk & Status Assessment Models

v2.0

DELIVERABLE NUMBER	D4.2
DELIVERABLE TITLE	Risk and Status Assessment Models
RESPONSIBLE AUTHOR	Antonis Koukourikos (SCiO)

TraceMyFish is part of the ERA-NET Cofund BlueBio with funding provided by national sources [i.e., General Secretariat for Research and Innovation in Greece, Research Council of Norway, Innovation Fund Denmark and Icelandic Centre for Research in Iceland] and co-funding by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program, Grant Agreement number 817992.

PROJECT ACRONYM	TraceMyFish
PROJECT FULL NAME	Traceability and Quality Monitoring throughout the Fish Value Chain
STARTING DATE (DUR.)	01/11/2021 (24 months)
ENDING DATE	31/10/2023
COORDINATOR	Panagiotis Zervas
COORDINATOR EMAIL	panagiotis@scio.systems
WORKPACKAGE N. TITLE	WP4 AI models for tracking and tracing
WORKPACKAGE LEADER	SCiO
RESPONSIBLE AUTHOR	Antonis Koukourikos (SCiO)
RESPONSIBLE AUTHOR EMAIL	antonis@scio.systems
DATE OF DELIVERY (CONTRACTUAL)	31/10/2023
DATE OF DELIVERY (SUBMITTED)	31/10/2023
VERSION STATUS	1.0
NATURE	REPORT
DISSEMINATION LEVEL	PUBLIC
AUTHORS (PARTNER)	Antonis Koukourikos (SCiO)
CONTRIBUTORS	-
REVIEWER	Panagiotis Zervas (SCiO)

VERSION	MODIFICATION(S)	DATE	AUTHOR(S)
v0.1	Initial ToC	01.09.2023	Antonis Koukourikos (SCiO)
v0.2	Section 2	15.09.2023	Antonis Koukourikos (SCiO)
v0.6	Section 3 & Section 4	15.10.2023	Antonis Koukourikos (SCiO)
v0.8	Full draft	29.10.2022	Antonis Koukourikos (SCiO)
v0.9	Internal review	27.04.2022	Panagiotis Zervas (SCiO)
v1.0	Document submitted	15.11.2023	Panagiotis Zervas (SCiO)

PARTICIPANTS		CONTACT PERSON
<p>SCiO P.C. (SCiO, Greece) Coordinator</p>		<p>Panagiotis Zervas E-mail: panagiotis@scio.systems</p>
<p>Department of Food Science and Human Nutrition, Agricultural University of Athens (AUA, Greece)</p>		<p>George-John Nychas E-mail: gjn@aua.gr</p>
<p>Department of Biotechnology and Food, Norwegian University of Science and Technology Science (NTNU, Norway)</p>		<p>Jørgen Lerfall E-mail: jorgen.lerfall@ntnu.no</p>
<p>Videometer A/S (VIDEOM, Denmark)</p>		<p>Nette Schultz E-mail: NS@videometer.com</p>
<p>Faculty of Food Science and Nutrition, University of Iceland (UoI, Iceland)</p>		<p>Maria Guðjónsdóttir E-mail: mariagu@hi.is</p>
<p>Matis (MATIS, Iceland)</p>		<p>Hildur Inga Sveinsdóttir E-mail: hilduringa@matis.is</p>

ACRONYMS LIST

ML	Machine Learning
IoT	Internet-of-Things
CNN	Convolutional Neural Networks
CLNN	Cascade Learning Networks

TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	7
1 INTRODUCTION.....	8
2 MODEL DESIGN METHODOLOGY.....	9
3 THE TRACEMYFISH PREDICTIVE MODELS	10
3.1 ATLANTIC SALMON VALUE CHAIN	10
3.1.1 Stress - AMPC.....	10
3.1.2 Stress - BP.....	10
3.1.3 Stress - H2S.....	11
3.1.4 Stress - Power	11
3.1.5 Stress - PSD	11
3.1.6 Stress - APPC	12
3.1.7 Melanin spot detection	12
3.1.8 Product freshness - QIM.....	12
3.2 ATLANTIC WHITEFISH VALUE CHAIN	13
3.2.1 Freshness assessment - eyes.....	13
3.2.2 Freshness assessment - gills.....	13
3.2.3 Freshness assessment - head.....	13
3.2.4 Freshness assessment - tail	14
3.2.5 Freshness assessment - QIM.....	14
3.2.6 Texture and freshness - TVC.....	14
3.2.7 Texture and freshness - Thickness.....	15
3.3 MEDITERRANEAN SEABREAM VALUE CHAIN	15
3.3.1 Microbiological quality assessment – vacuum packaged, trained over measurements from product skin on marine agar	15
3.3.2 Microbiological quality assessment – vacuum packaged, trained over PCA measurements from product skin.....	15
3.3.3 Microbiological quality assessment – vacuum packaged, trained over measurements from product flesh on marine agar.....	16

3.3.4	Microbiological quality assessment – vacuum packaged, trained over PCA measurements from product flesh	16
3.3.5	Microbiological quality assessment – air packaged, trained over measurements from product skin on marine agar.....	16
3.3.6	Microbiological quality assessment – air packaged, trained over PCA measurements from product skin	17
3.3.7	Microbiological quality assessment – air packaged, trained over measurements from product flesh on marine agar.....	17
3.3.8	Microbiological quality assessment – air packaged, trained over PCA measurements from product flesh	17
4	MODEL INTEGRATION	18
5	CONCLUSION.....	19

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present report summarises the methodological approach for designing and building the TraceMyFish predictive models in the context of the TraceMyFish pilots. As the pilots covered different challenges faced across the three examined value chains, different models corresponding to the pilot analyses were trained and deployed. The structure and performance of all models are included in the report, along with some observations on their efficiency and generalization capacity, a critical aspect for deploying the models in realistic settings.

The models were further integrated in the TraceMyFish iFMS and are accessible via the relevant user-facing applications, as defined in the TraceMyFish iFMS architecture.

1 INTRODUCTION

TraceMyFish aims to advance supply system in three geographically distributed blue bioeconomy value chains, by designing and implementing an iFish Management System (iFMS) that will allow the tracking and tracing of safety and quality-critical information across the links of the targeted value chains. Moreover, the TraceMyFish iFMS will establish a secure, trust-enabled data infrastructure, which will collect, pre-process and analyse data coming from innovative, portable sensing devices of different nature and modality and informing specialized AI models and architecture that will enable timely risk prediction to different value chain actors.

Towards this objective, Work Package 4, Risk and Status Assessment Models, aims to design, train and deploy the machine learning components that will perform the predictive analysis to assess the status and quality of a fish product as it goes through the value chains targeted by TraceMyFish.

It builds on the scientific analyses of WP2 and the experimental designs and protocols employed in WP6, to identify important features, and define targeted variables and collaborates closely with WP3 to clarify the association of experimentally observed features with measurements taken as the value chain progresses. Finally, it follows the architectural choices of WP5 to appropriately package and integrate the software components that operationalise the machine learning solutions.

The present document describes the process for building the TraceMyFish predictive models for the different pilots and the different problems analysed on each of these pilots and summarises the achieved model performance for each case. Section 2 presents the employed methodological approach; Section 3 continues with the presentation of results on a per-pilot and per-problem basis; Section 4 describes the positioning of the predictive models in the overall TraceMyFish iFMS architecture; Finally, Section 5 summarises and concludes the report.

2 MODEL DESIGN METHODOLOGY

To efficiently tackle the different predictive cases set by the project pilots, a process for automatically building neural architectures for the different problems was set up, producing different networks for the different predictive problems.

The neural networks implementing the prediction model were discovered through an automated architecture generation and validation process, aiming to specify the simplest (shallowest) architecture that achieves the optimal precision/generalization capacity/explainability balance. The generator produces multi-layered feed-forward neural networks organised in a cascaded topology (Fahlman, 1990). Each neuron in the network uses a hyperbolic tangent as its activation function, because of its antisymmetric properties. The exception is the output layer, where the node(s) use a linear activation function.

The training of the models was performed in batch mode, i.e., all training data were fed to the network under training simultaneously. Training followed the iRprop methodology ((Riedmiller, 1993), (Igel, 2003)), which uses only the sign of the error function gradient to propagate the gradient. Thus, it is more robust with respect to its ability to manage very large or very small gradient values, avoiding possible overflow and precision issues respectively.

The training process for all models entailed the configuration of the network builder with different parameters values for the targeted MSE and the split of the available dataset into training and testing subsets, in order to determine the architecture with sufficient performance and generalisation capacity.

The general characteristics and performance of the optimal networks for each pilot are presented in the following section.

3 THE TRACEMYFISH PREDICTIVE MODELS

As reported in detail in deliverable D6.2, the TraceMyFish pilots conducted variegating experiments tackling the major challenges faced in their respective targeted value chains. For each challenge, different laboratory experiments were conducted, with their results associated with measurements taken using VideometerLite, the sensor integrated in the TraceMyFish platform.

In all cases, and while additional measurements from sophisticated laboratory-level instruments were used for cross-checking the analytical results, the VideometerLite measurements were the sole input variables for the documents, apart from basic information also captured in the value chain, i.e., timing of measurement, temperature, and storage medium where applicable. The purpose of all pilot designs and of the developed predictive models is to simulate as realistically as possible the conditions of the different value chains as they unfold and assess the effectiveness of the TraceMyFish sensing/predicting proposition for tackling the specific value chain challenges.

The following subsections describe in brief the data collected and submitted for analysis from each pilot, the models developed for each predictive problem, and their performance under the prism of balancing accuracy and generalisation capacity, as described in the methodology. In summary, models were developed for the following challenges:

1. **Atlantic Salmon Value Chain:** QIM score for whole fish, melanin spot detection, stress factor for salmon fillet (AMPC, BP, H2S, PSD, APPC, Power)
2. **Atlantic Whitefish Value Chain:** QIM, freshness detection from different parts (eyes, gills, head, tail), texture and freshness (TVC)
3. **Mediterranean Seabream Value Chain:** Microbiological quality (TVC) measured under different packaging (vacuum, air), from different product parts (skin, flesh), and from different product origins (aquaculture, supermarket).

3.1 ATLANTIC SALMON VALUE CHAIN

3.1.1 Stress - AMPC

Parameter	Value
Number of Hidden Layers	3
Total Nodes	5
Total Connections	162
LMS Capacity	34

Metric	Value
Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	0.369
Mean Square Error (MSE)	0.261
Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)	0.511
R-squared (R ²)	0.952

3.1.2 Stress - BP

Parameter	Value
Number of Hidden Layers	124
Total Nodes	349
Total Connections	22272
LMS Capacity	155

Metric	Value
Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	0.229
Mean Square Error (MSE)	0.224
Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)	0.473
R-squared (R ²)	0.992

3.1.3 Stress - H2S

Parameter	Value
Number of Hidden Layers	7
Total Nodes	10
Total Connections	346
LMS Capacity	38

Metric	Value
Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	0.359
Mean Square Error (MSE)	0.299
Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)	0.547
R-squared (R ²)	0.939

3.1.4 Stress - Power

Parameter	Value
Number of Hidden Layers	61
Total Nodes	135
Total Connections	7522
LMS Capacity	92

Metric	Value
Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	0.271
Mean Square Error (MSE)	0.166
Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)	0.407
R-squared (R ²)	0.994

3.1.5 Stress - PSD

Parameter	Value
Number of Hidden Layers	6
Total Nodes	11
Total Connections	368
LMS Capacity	37

Metric	Value
Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	0.353
Mean Square Error (MSE)	0.276
Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)	0.525

R-squared (R2)	0.952
----------------	-------

3.1.6 Stress - APPC

Parameter	Value
Number of Hidden Layers	6
Total Nodes	15
Total Connections	493
LMS Capacity	37

Metric	Value
Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	0.310
Mean Square Error (MSE)	0.160
Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)	0.399
R-squared (R2)	0.971

3.1.7 Melanin spot detection

Parameter	Value
Number of Hidden Layers	2
Total Nodes	4
Total Connections	67
LMS Capacity	18

Metric	Value
False Classified Examples (FCE)	4
False Positive Ratio (FPR)	0.010
False Negative Ratio (FNR)	0.188
True Positive Ratio (TPR) / Sensitivity / Recall	0.813
True Negative Ratio (TNR) / Specificity	0.990
Accuracy (ACC)	0.967
Balanced Accuracy (BACC)	0.901
Positive Predictive Value (PPV) / Precision	0.929
F1 Score (F1)	0.867
Fowlkes-Mallows index (FM)	0.869
Jaccard index (JI) / Critical Success index (CSI)	0.765

3.1.8 Product freshness - QIM

Parameter	Value
Number of Hidden Layers	47
Total Nodes	206
Total Connections	LMS Capacity
LMS Capacity	66

Metric	Value
Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	0.358

Mean Square Error (MSE)	0.294
Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)	0.542
R-squared (R2)	0.995

3.2 ATLANTIC WHITEFISH VALUE CHAIN

3.2.1 Freshness assessment - eyes

Parameter	Value
Number of Hidden Layers	4
Total Nodes	8
Total Connections	235
LMS Capacity	32

Metric	Value
Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	0.326
Mean Square Error (MSE)	0.193
Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)	0.439
R-squared (R2)	0.995

3.2.2 Freshness assessment - gills

Parameter	Value
Number of Hidden Layers	5
Total Nodes	11
Total Connections	328
LMS Capacity	33

Metric	Value
Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	0.280
Mean Square Error (MSE)	0.153
Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)	0.392
R-squared (R2)	0.996

3.2.3 Freshness assessment - head

Parameter	Value
Number of Hidden Layers	6
Total Nodes	18
Total Connections	539
LMS Capacity	34

Metric	Value
Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	0.363
Mean Square Error (MSE)	0.250
Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)	0.500

R-squared (R ²)	0.994
-----------------------------	-------

3.2.4 Freshness assessment - tail

Parameter	Value
Number of Hidden Layers	6
Total Nodes	10
Total Connections	301
LMS Capacity	34

Metric	Value
Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	0.434
Mean Square Error (MSE)	0.299
Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)	0.546
R-squared (R ²)	0.992

3.2.5 Freshness assessment - QIM

Parameter	Value
Number of Hidden Layers	25
Total Nodes	213
Total Connections	7573
LMS Capacity	54

Metric	Value
Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	0.348
Mean Square Error (MSE)	0.299
Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)	0.548
R-squared (R ²)	0.992

3.2.6 Texture and freshness - TVC

Parameter	Value
Number of Hidden Layers	0
Total Nodes	1
Total Connections	29
LMS Capacity	29

Metric	Value
Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	0.431
Mean Square Error (MSE)	0.280
Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)	0.529
R-squared (R ²)	0.893

3.2.7 Texture and freshness - Thickness

Parameter	Value
Number of Hidden Layers	139
Total Nodes	386
Total Connections	28458
LMS Capacity	168

Metric	Value
Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	0.359
Mean Square Error (MSE)	0.250
Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)	0.500
R-squared (R2)	0.909

3.3 MEDITERRANEAN SEABREAM VALUE CHAIN

3.3.1 Microbiological quality assessment – vacuum packaged, trained over measurements from product skin on marine agar

Parameter	Value
Number of Hidden Layers	13
Total Nodes	33
Total Connections	1156
LMS Capacity	43

Metric	Value
Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	0.388
Mean Square Error (MSE)	0.250
Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)	0.500
R-squared (R2)	0.786

3.3.2 Microbiological quality assessment – vacuum packaged, trained over PCA measurements from product skin

Parameter	Value
Number of Hidden Layers	5
Total Nodes	7
Total Connections	226
LMS Capacity	35

Metric	Value
Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	0.416
Mean Square Error (MSE)	0.282
Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)	0.531
R-squared (R2)	0.740

3.3.3 Microbiological quality assessment – vacuum packaged, trained over measurements from product flesh on marine agar

Parameter	Value
Number of Hidden Layers	7
Total Nodes	13
Total Connections	420
LMS Capacity	37

Metric	Value
Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	0.413
Mean Square Error (MSE)	0.300
Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)	0.547
R-squared (R ²)	0.825

3.3.4 Microbiological quality assessment – vacuum packaged, trained over PCA measurements from product flesh

Parameter	Value
Number of Hidden Layers	21
Total Nodes	150
Total Connections	5338
LMS Capacity	51

Metric	Value
Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	0.406
Mean Square Error (MSE)	0.283
Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)	0.547
R-squared (R ²)	0.835

3.3.5 Microbiological quality assessment – air packaged, trained over measurements from product skin on marine agar

Parameter	Value
Number of Hidden Layers	91
Total Nodes	199
Total Connections	11961
LMS Capacity	121

Metric	Value
Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	0.408
Mean Square Error (MSE)	0.284
Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)	0.533
R-squared (R ²)	0.815

3.3.6 Microbiological quality assessment – air packaged, trained over PCA measurements from product skin

Parameter	Value
Number of Hidden Layers	34
Total Nodes	38
Total Connections	1821
LMS Capacity	64

Metric	Value
Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	0.393
Mean Square Error (MSE)	0.272
Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)	0.522
R-squared (R ²)	0.839

3.3.7 Microbiological quality assessment – air packaged, trained over measurements from product flesh on marine agar

Parameter	Value
Number of Hidden Layers	35
Total Nodes	785
Total Connections	29900
LMS Capacity	65

Metric	Value
Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	0.398
Mean Square Error (MSE)	0.269
Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)	0.519
R-squared (R ²)	0.841

3.3.8 Microbiological quality assessment – air packaged, trained over PCA measurements from product flesh

Parameter	Value
Number of Hidden Layers	50
Total Nodes	148
Total Connections	6809
LMS Capacity	80

Metric	Value
Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	0.414
Mean Square Error (MSE)	0.299
Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)	0.519
R-squared (R ²)	0.866

4 MODEL INTEGRATION

The neural network architectures derived through the methodology described in Section 2 were implemented as Python scripts and deployed as dockerised services in the data platform serving the TraceMyFish iFMS, in accordance with the architecture developed in the context of WP5.

From there, the models are accessible via calls to the relevant API, used from the user-facing applications also developed in the context of WP5. From there, users can register a tracked sample within one of the covered value chains, add measurements for the sample and enact the predictive model for the issue they want to monitor. The user-facing app can be accessed at: <https://scio-data-science.shinyapps.io/tracemyfish-shinyapp>. More details on the apps and the way they use the models are presented in the relevant D5.2 (v2.0) deliverable.

5 CONCLUSION

The report describes the methodology for building neural network architectures tackling the predictive problems posed by the TraceMyFish pilots and using solely measurements able to be collected across the value chains as model inputs. The selected architectures balance performance and generalisation capacity in order to ensure that the models will remain performant as they are used in real-world contexts.

In general terms, the performance achieved was particularly promising for all pilot challenges. However, some of the problems, such as: the prediction of the BP and HS parameters in the Salmon Pilot; the prediction of Thickness in the Whitefish pilot; and the prediction of microbial quality on air packaging conditions for the Seabream pilot, required relatively extensive and complex architectures to be solved with sufficient accuracy. The fact implies that further improvement pathways are possible, using possibly additional measurement and monitoring devices or periodically feeding the system with laboratory measurements of product samples. These point to promising directions for the extension of the TraceMyFish iFMs in the future and the establishment of products with broader coverage.